

Basic Software Skills in the Desi Countries

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Between 2016 and 2021 they grew by 1.45%

Desi Index calculates the value of basic software skills. It is a variable that considers some skills such as Word processing, the use of the advanced functions of the calculation sheet, with the possibility of creating a presentation or text document, with images and tables or graphics, whether it is written in a programming language.

Ranking of European countries for the value of basic software skills in the Desi countries in 2021.

The Netherlands is in the first place for the value of basic software skills with a value equal to 20.02, followed by Finland with a value of 19, 26 units, and Sweden with a value of 18.38 units. In the middle of the standings there are Slovenia with a value of 14.66 units, followed by Lithuania with a value of 14.51 units and from Malta with an amount of 14.38 units. Latvia closes the ranking with an amount of 10.97 units, followed by Romania with a value of 8.77 units and by Bulgaria with an amount equal to 7.72 units.

Ranking of the countries of the percentage variation of basic software skills between 2016 and 2021.

Romania is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the value of basic software skills between 2016 and 2021 with a value equal to 22.44% equal to an amount of 1.61 units, followed by Ireland with an amount of 16.69% equal to an amount of 1.69 units, followed by Greece with an amount of 10.54% equal to an amount of 1.33 units. In the middle of the standings there are Croatia with an amount of 2.61% equal to an amount of 0.36 units, followed by Spain with an amount equal to a value of 2.41% equal to a value of 0.35 units, and from Finland with a value of 1.94% equal to an amount of 0.37 units. At the end of the ranking there are Bulgaria with an amount of -7.14% equal to an amount of -0.59 units, followed by Denmark with an amount of -12.24% equal to an amount of -2.45 units and from Latvia with an amount of -13.73% equal to an amount of -1.75 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization using the K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. The result shows the presence of the following Clusters or:

- Cluster 1: Malta, Slovenia, Croatia, Spain, Cyprus, Ireland, Latvia, Slovakia, France, Italy, Poland, Czech Republic, Estonia, Belgium;
- Cluster 2: Finland, Sweden, Netherlands, Denmark, Germany, Austria, Luxembourg;
- Cluster 3: Bulgaria, Romania.

From a strictly metric point of view, it appears that the value of the median of the 2-C2 cluster is equal to 17.93 units, the value of the median of the 1-C1 cluster is equal to an amount of 13.99 units and the value of the median of the Cluster 3-C3 is equal to 8.24 units. The presence of the following system of the Clusters or: $C2 = 17.93 > C1 = 13.99 > C3 = 8.24$. From the point of view of economic

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geography it appears that Scandinavia and Northern Europe have a high value compared to the value of central Europe and Eastern Europe.

Network Analysis with Manhattan's distance. The network analysis is applied below with the distance of Manhattan to check if there are structures that determine relations between the various countries of the Desi Index. There is a complex relationship between the following countries namely: Spain, Slovenia, Croatia, Lithuania, Malta, Portugal, Greece. Particularly:

- Malta has a connection with Portugal for a value of 0.29 units, and with Lithuania for a value of 0.17 units;
- Portugal has a connection with Malta for an amount equal to 0.29 units, with Greece for a value of 0.29 units and with Lithuania for a value of 0.3 units;
- Greece has a connection with Portugal for a value of 0.29 units;
- Lithuania has Portugal a connection for an amount equal to 0.3 units, with mortar for a value of 0.17 units, with Croatia for an amount equal to 0.29 units, with Spain for an equal amount to a value of 0.29 units and with Slovenia for a value of 0.18 units;
- Spain has a connection with Lithuania for a value of 0.29 units, with Croatia for a value of 0.3, and with Slovenia for a value of 0.23 units;
- Croatia has a connection with Lithuania for a value of 0.29 units, with Spain for a value of 0.3 units, and with Slovenia for a value of 0.18 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with Lithuania for a value of 0.18 units, with Spain for a value of 0.23 units and with Croatia for a value of 0.18 units.

There are also simplified network structure or consisting of only two nodes or:

- Austria and Germany have a connection for a value of 0.22;
- Belgium and Estonia have a connection for a value of 0.28 units.

The analysis shows that the most connected country is Lithuania.

Conclusions. The analysis shows that basic software skills grew on average in the period between 2016 and 2021 of an amount of 1.45% or equal to an amount of 0.21 units. In addition, in 2021 on average the value of basic software skills was equal to an amount of 14.51 units. Although the fact that basic software skills have grown in the period between 2016 and 2021 is certainly appreciable, it is also true that this value from the absolute point of view is still reduced. In fact, the use of Word, Excel, knowing how to make presentations or write complex documents should be much more widespread at the European population. The spread of these IT skills is necessary to make sure that the European economy is oriented towards the economy of knowledge and economy of technological innovation. It follows that the development of basic software skills at the European population must be pursued using economic policies capable of increasing basic software skills.

Competenze Softweristiche di Base

<i>Countries</i>	<i>2016</i>	<i>2017</i>	<i>2018</i>	<i>2019</i>	<i>2020</i>	<i>2021</i>	<i>Var Ass</i>	<i>Var Per</i>
<i>Austria</i>	★ 17,29	★ 17,25	★ 17,78	★ 17,78	★ 17,13	★ 17,13	★ -0,16	★ -0,94
<i>Belgium</i>	★ 15,63	★ 16,01	★ 15,75	★ 15,75	★ 15,56	★ 15,56	★ -0,07	★ -0,46
<i>Bulgaria</i>	★ 8,32	★ 7,08	★ 7,73	★ 7,73	★ 7,72	★ 7,72	★ -0,59	★ -7,14
<i>Croatia</i>	★ 13,65	★ 14,62	★ 14,31	★ 14,31	★ 14,00	★ 14,00	★ 0,36	★ 2,61
<i>Cyprus</i>	★ 12,32	★ 11,59	★ 13,59	★ 13,59	★ 11,57	★ 11,57	★ -0,74	★ -6,04
<i>Czechia</i>	★ 15,02	★ 14,15	★ 15,61	★ 15,61	★ 16,04	★ 16,04	★ 1,02	★ 6,82
<i>Denmark</i>	★ 20,04	★ 19,72	★ 18,08	★ 18,08	★ 17,59	★ 17,59	★ -2,45	★ -12,24
<i>Estonia</i>	★ 16,37	★ 15,25	★ 15,37	★ 15,37	★ 15,61	★ 15,61	★ -0,75	★ -4,59
<i>Finland</i>	★ 18,89	★ 18,89	★ 19,04	★ 19,04	★ 19,26	★ 19,26	★ 0,37	★ 1,94
<i>France</i>	★ 15,25	★ 14,73	★ 15,06	★ 15,06	★ 15,01	★ 15,01	★ -0,23	★ -1,54
<i>Germany</i>	★ 17,30	★ 17,48	★ 17,54	★ 17,54	★ 17,94	★ 17,94	★ 0,64	★ 3,69
<i>Greece</i>	★ 12,64	★ 13,35	★ 13,04	★ 13,04	★ 13,98	★ 13,98	★ 1,33	★ 10,54
<i>Hungary</i>	★ 13,03	★ 13,53	★ 13,02	★ 13,02	★ 12,66	★ 12,66	★ -0,37	★ -2,87
<i>Ireland</i>	★ 11,75	★ 11,49	★ 12,36	★ 12,36	★ 13,71	★ 13,71	★ 1,96	★ 16,69
<i>Italy</i>	★ 12,06	★ 12,10	★ 11,72	★ 11,72	★ 11,34	★ 11,34	★ -0,72	★ -5,94
<i>Latvia</i>	★ 12,72	★ 13,00	★ 12,23	★ 12,23	★ 10,97	★ 10,97	★ -1,75	★ -13,73
<i>Lithuania</i>	★ 13,46	★ 13,53	★ 14,25	★ 14,25	★ 14,51	★ 14,51	★ 1,05	★ 7,77
<i>Luxembourg</i>	★ 16,44	★ 16,54	★ 16,80	★ 16,80	★ 16,96	★ 16,96	★ 0,53	★ 3,20
<i>Malta</i>	★ 13,88	★ 12,98	★ 14,31	★ 14,31	★ 14,38	★ 14,38	★ 0,49	★ 3,54
<i>Netherlands</i>	★ 18,31	★ 19,44	★ 20,11	★ 20,11	★ 20,02	★ 20,02	★ 1,71	★ 9,35
<i>Poland</i>	★ 10,73	★ 11,78	★ 12,21	★ 12,21	★ 11,52	★ 11,52	★ 0,79	★ 7,36
<i>Portugal</i>	★ 13,38	★ 12,98	★ 13,66	★ 13,66	★ 13,75	★ 13,75	★ 0,37	★ 2,76
<i>Romania</i>	★ 7,16	★ 7,39	★ 7,88	★ 7,88	★ 8,77	★ 8,77	★ 1,61	★ 22,44
<i>Slovakia</i>	★ 14,14	★ 14,29	★ 15,72	★ 15,72	★ 13,89	★ 13,89	★ -0,24	★ -1,73
<i>Slovenia</i>	★ 13,58	★ 14,29	★ 14,23	★ 14,23	★ 14,66	★ 14,66	★ 1,08	★ 7,99
<i>Spain</i>	★ 14,47	★ 14,10	★ 14,47	★ 14,47	★ 14,82	★ 14,82	★ 0,35	★ 2,41
<i>Sweden</i>	★ 18,35	★ 17,43	★ 19,57	★ 19,57	★ 18,38	★ 18,38	★ 0,03	★ 0,18
<i>Media</i>	★ 14,30	★ 14,26	★ 14,65	★ 14,65	★ 14,51	★ 14,51	★ 0,21	★ 1,45

Declarations

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